

Full Length Research Paper

Textural changes of plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) finger regions during maturity

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Received 10 June 2019; Accepted 27 July, 2019

The textural properties of plantain (*Musa paradisiaca* Linn.) finger was investigated in this study. These textural properties (firmness, springiness, adhesiveness, chewiness, stringiness, fracturability, and gumminess) of the plantain fingers were measured using the Warner-Bratzler shear force (WBS) method. The plantain fingers were analyzed at three maturity stages (stage 5, 6 and 7) and three-finger regions (stalk, mid and blossom). Results obtained from the study showed that ripening (maturity) stage had significant ($P \leq 0.05$) effect on all the textural properties investigated. At each maturity stage, the finger's stalk region had the highest textural properties values, when compared to the mid and blossom regions. The results further depict that as ripening

progressed, all the textural properties declined, except the adhesiveness which showed marginal increment. From the results, the average fracturability declined from 11.70 N at stage 5 to 5.22 N at stage 7 of ripening, while the average firmness decreased from 12.21 N to 5.7 N during ripening. The average stringiness of the plantain fingers decreased significantly from 18.92 N to 17.77 N during ripening. The results obtained from this research would help in planning plantain bunch harvesting, handling, and processing operations efficiently.

Keywords: Instrumental texture analysis, plantain finger, texture, ripening, maturity

INTRODUCTION

Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca* Linn.) with world production index of over thirty-five million tons in 2016 (FAOSTAT, 2018), is fast becoming an important fruit eaten both ripe and unripe. According to Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), Nigeria produced about three million tons in 2016. Plantain cultivation in Nigeria is concentrated in the southern part of the country, due to the favorable environmental conditions. Plantains require about 3 months from the beginning of flowering until harvest. Multiple fingers are produced on a large bunch, weighing between 13 kg to 45 kg. Within the bunch are clusters of double rows of fruit called 'hands', and individual fruit called 'fingers' (NFCL, 2003).

The major postharvest problems of plantains are mechanical damages during handling, over ripening and pathological damage by microorganisms (Aborisade and Akomolafe, 2007; Nyorere and Uguru, 2018a). The average shelf life of mature green plantain finger stored at 12°C is between 4 to 5 weeks. But if the finger is harvested at a more advanced ripening stage or stored at a higher temperature, the shelf life will be less than 2 weeks (Ecofog, 2018). Overripe fruits are likely to become soft and/or mealy in texture soon after harvest; therefore, they usually have lower post-harvest storage ability.

Maturity at harvest is the most important factor that

determines postharvest-life and final quality such as appearance, texture, flavor, nutritive value of fruit-vegetables. Maturity standards for plantains are less precise than they are for bananas. Several different external and internal fruit characteristics can be used to determine plantain maturity. These include fruit diameter, age of the bunch, angularity of the fruit, length of the fruit, and peel colour (NFCL, 2003). Fruits picked at less than mature stages are subject to greater shriveling and mechanical damage, and are of inferior flavor quality. The necessity of shipping mature fruit-vegetables for long distances has often encouraged harvesting them at less than ideal maturity, resulting in suboptimal taste quality to the consumer (Kader, 1996; El-Ramady *et al.*, 2015). During ripening of plantain finger, its physical, mechanical and chemical properties are altered. For instance, plantain's finger skin color change from green to yellow during maturity/ripening; the firmness and elasticity decreases during ripening; while the carbohydrate in the finger pulp is converted into sugar during maturity/ripening (Tapre and Jain, 2012).

Texture is a division of sensory quality in food products, and texture profile analysis (TPA) is one of the methods that have been employed in analyzing the textural properties of food materials (Kajuna *et al.*, 1997). Knowledge of the changes in the textural properties of plantain fingers during maturity and ripening is an important attributes to food scientists. This is because textural changes in plantain's finger during ripening involved significant changes in its texture profile. Some researchers have studied the textural profile of plantain and banana fingers, during maturation. Mustaffa *et al.* (1998), investigated the texture profile of banana (cv. *Montel*) during development and maturation by means of penetrometric studies, and reported that the texture values of the fingers decreased significantly during maturation. Tapre and Jain, (2012) reported that the cohesiveness of the banana fingers declined from 0.06 to 0.04; while the firmness of decreased significantly from 37.29N at 5th stage to 22.57N at 7th stage of ripening. In addition, Chauhan *et al.*, (2006) investigated the textural changes in banana during ripening under active and passive modified atmosphere, and observed that the hardness, springiness and cohesiveness declined during ripening, while the adhesiveness inclined during ripening. Firmness of the plantain finger is the maximum force the finger can withstand during the first biting (compression). Springiness (elasticity) is the distance of compression cycle during the second bite, that is, rate at which the deformed plantain finger reforms; adhesiveness is the rate at which the plantain finger's pulp pulls away from probe or roof of mouth/teeth (organoleptic); Chewiness is the energy required to chew the cucumber flesh until it is ready for swallowing (Steffe, 1996; Nyorere and Uguru, 2018b). Gumminess is the force required to disintegrate a plantain pulp/flesh to the state when it can be swallowed; and it is the product of firmness and cohesiveness. While

chewiness is the energy required to masticate a solid/semisolid food before swallowing (Chauhan *et al.*, 2006).

Although, the many authors have worked on the textural quality of fruits and vegetables; however, there is paucity of information on the textural changes in plantain finger during ripening/maturity, with respects to its three regions (stalk, mid and blossom). Therefore, the objectives of this study were to: (i) investigate textural properties of plantains as affected by advanced maturity stages, and (ii) compare the influence of finger region on the textural properties of plantain finger.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material selection

Twenty plantain plants were tagged randomly from March to April 2018 during flower emergence in a plantain plantation in Ozoro, Delta State, Nigeria. The fingers growth was observed weekly, until ripening of the fingers started in the plantain bunch. The plantain fingers used for this study were harvested at three stages of advanced ripening/maturity stages, which were stages 5, 6 and 7. Standard color chart (Figure 1) approved by USDA for plantain and banana fingers was used for categorizing the plantain fingers into the various maturity stages. After harvesting of the plantain fingers, they were selected based on these categories; uniformity of size and shape, no visible sign of mechanical damage, freedom from pests and diseases attacks. Extremely large and small fingers were discarded. The selected plantain fingers were immediately transported to the Material Testing Laboratory of the National Center for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria, for the Texture Profile Analysis. Special precautions were taken to minimize mechanical damage of the plantain fingers during transportation by lining the boxes underneath and corners with foam material.

Texture profile analysis (TPA)

An instrumental TPA's test was performed on the plantain fingers using the Warner-Bratzler shear force (WBS) method, with the aid of the Universal Testing Machine (Testometric model). The three plantains finger's regions tested in the study are shown in (Figure 2). The puncture test, which is one of the instrumental textural profile analysis methods, was employed with the following parameters; 6 mm cylindrical probe, 105 mm/min crosshead speed and 200 mm/min preload speed. For each test, individual sample (cut out section of the plantain finger region) was positioned in the machine on the longitudinal axis, and held firmly with two fingers. At the preset crosshead speed (105 mm/min), the probe

Figure 1. Standard Colour chart for plantain and banana.
Source: Tapre and Jain (2012).

Figure 2. A plantain finger showing the three regions.

penetrated the sample to a present depth (50% of the sample height 'diameter'), and then returned to the point where pre-load was reached on the first cycle. Then the probe waited for some seconds, which represent the time between chews, before it punctured the sample for the second time in the same position. The penetration depth was set to 50% of each finger's diameter; because deeper penetration greater than 50% will significantly cause fluctuation of the measured TPA parameters, mostly the firmness, gumminess and chewiness (Mavroudis *et al.*, 2004). At the end of each penetration test, these TPA parameters (firmness, springiness, adhesiveness, chewiness, stringiness, fracturability and

gumminess) were measured and calculated automatically by the microprocessor of the universal testing machine, and the results read from the computer screen. All the tests were carried out at ambient temperature ($27 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$). Each test on each finger region was replicated ten times, and the average value recorded.

Statistical analysis

The data obtained were subjected to Analysis of variance, by using the SPSS statistical software (version 20.0, SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL). The difference between

mean values of parameters was investigated using Duncan's multiple range tests at 95% confidence level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study explained the instrumental texture profile analysis of plantain finger region during maturity/ripening. The analyses of variance (ANOVA) of the effect of plantain finger region and maturity stage on the textural qualities of plantain finger region, and their separated means according to Duncan Multiple Range Test are presented in (Tables 1 and 2). As shown in (Table 1), ripening stage had significant ($P \leq 0.05$) effect on the seven TPA parameters investigated. Whereas, the finger region did not significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) influenced all the TPA parameters investigated in this research. According to (Table 1), the interaction of finger region and maturity stage did not significantly influenced the all the TPA parameters of the plantain finger.

Instrumental texture profile analysis

The effect of maturity stage and finger region on the textural qualities of plantain fingers regions tested (stalk, mid and blossom) are presented in (Figures 3 to 9). As shown in (Figures 3 to 9), there were insignificant differences in the textural qualities among the three finger's regions tested. The results indicated that as the ripening progressed from stage 5 to stage 7, these TPA parameters (firmness, springiness, chewiness, stringiness, fracturability and gumminess) of the plantain fingers declined consistently. But the fingers adhesiveness increased marginally with ripening of the fingers from stage 5 to stage 7. The increased adhesiveness during ripening can be attributed to the enhanced solubilization, and it helps in establishing the relationship between structural changes and ripening stages (Chauhan *et al.*, 2006).

The results showed a consistent decline in the plantain finger's firmness during maturity (Figure 3). In addition, a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in firmness was found at the different maturity stages of the plantain finger. The softening of the plantain finger during the advance maturity stage (stage 7), when ripening was noticeable could be attributed to the alteration in cell wall structure by degrading enzymes (e.g. polygalacturonase) (Seymour, 1993). Textural qualities changes in plantain and banana finger during maturity/ripening is mainly due to the biochemical changes within cellular structure of the fingers pulp. According to Ali (2004), 50% firmness loss occurred in 3 days during ripening in Mas banana (*Musa acuminata*, AA group).

As shown in (Figure 4), there was no significant difference finger's springiness between the ripening stage 6 and 7, but significant difference occurred between

ripening stages 5 and 6. These results (0.83 Nm at stage 5 and 0.73 Nm at stage 5) suggested that lesser mastication energy will be required to chew the plantain finger flesh as maturity progresses. Similar results were reported by Soltani *et al.* (2011), Chauhan *et al.* (2006) and Kajuna *et al.* (1997) on plantain and banana fingers, where they observed general declined in the textural qualities of banana fingers during ripening. Kajuna *et al.* (1997) observed that the springiness of plantain fingers during storage decreased from 0.436 to 0.407 after eight days, which is similar to over results.

It can be observed from the results shown in (Table 2) that the plantain fingers recorded steadier increment in the adhesiveness during the maturity across the three finger's regions (Figure 5). According to Chauhan *et al.* (2006) the increment in adhesiveness of plantain pulp during ripening can be attributed to its mucilaginous nature which increases during maturity. In addition, it was observed that the gumminess of the plantain finger decreased significantly during ripening (Figure 6). Similar results were obtained by Kajuna *et al.* (1997) who reported that the gumminess of the plantain finger decreased significantly from 8.4 N on day 1 to 5.1 N on day 4 of storage; while the chewiness decreased from 4.99 to 2.9 N during eight days storage period.

As shown in (Figure 7), the average stringiness of the plantain fingers decreased significantly from 18.92 N at 5th stage to 18.06 N at 6th stage of maturity. Also, the fracturability decreased significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) as the finger ripened (Figure 8). From the results, the fracturability declined from 11.70 N at stage 5 to 5.22 N at stage 7 of ripening. The results indicated that as the maturity progressed, the chewiness of the fingers decreased significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) stage 5 to stage 7 (Figure 9). The average chewiness of plantain fingers decreased significantly from 2.19 N at 5th stage to 1.12 N at 7th stage of ripening. Similar trends were observed by Tapre and Jain, (2012) and Soltani *et al.* (2010) on the mechanical/textural properties of banana fingers during maturity. Tapre and Jain, (2012) observed that the chewiness of banana finger declined from 4.8 to 2.68, during the ripening. While Soltani *et al.* (2010) reported that the ultimate strength of banana fingers decreased dramatically between stage 1 and stage 3 and then continued to decrease at a slower rate thereafter. In addition, Salvador *et al.*, (2007) studied the changes in texture of banana during storage at 10°C and 20°C; and observed that the flesh texture of the *M. Cavendish* type bananas softened quite rapidly during storage. The results shown that plantain fingers are highly susceptible to textural changes during maturity and ripening process, and these changes need closer attention during storage period. Studies on the textural changes in banana during ripening involve significant changes in the texture profile (Kajuna *et al.*, 1997). Thompson, (1996) reported that the softening of banana fruit during ripening treatment is associated with the conversion of starch to sugar, the

Table 1. Analysis of variance of effect of maturity stage and finger region on the textural qualities of plantain finger.

Source	df	Firmness	Spr	Adh	Che	Str	Fra	Gum
P	2	0.1098 ^{ns}	0.3351 ^{ns}	0.2179 ^{ns}	0.1029 ^{ns}	0.4948 ^{ns}	0.4167 ^{ns}	0.2411 ^{ns}
M	2	9.78E-18*	6.7E-05*	3.7E-14*	5.8E-17*	3.8E-03*	1.82E-17*	1.0E-11*
P x M	4	0.9351 ^{ns}	0.9978 ^{ns}	0.9993 ^{ns}	0.9994 ^{ns}	0.9945 ^{ns}	0.9664 ^{ns}	0.9947 ^{ns}

P = finger region; M = maturity stage; * = significant at $p \leq 0.05$; ns = not significant; Spr = Springiness; Adh = Adhesiveness; Che = Chewiness; Str = Stringiness; Fra = Fracturability; Gum = Gumminess

Table 2. Summary results of the textural qualities of plantain finger during maturity

Parameter	Maturity stage	Finger region					
		Stalk		Mid		Blossom	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Firmness (N)	Stage 5	12.36 ^a	0.29	12.21 ^{ab}	0.16	12.07 ^b	0.16
	Stage 6	10.13 ^a	0.90	9.62 ^{ab}	0.80	9.28 ^b	0.69
	Stage 7	6.18 ^a	0.86	5.58 ^{ab}	0.92	5.35 ^b	0.94
Springiness (Nm)	Stage 5	0.838 ^a	0.027	0.825 ^a	0.023	0.812 ^a	0.025
	Stage 6	0.757 ^b	0.065	0.742 ^b	0.061	0.735 ^b	0.058
	Stage 7	0.755 ^b	0.038	0.73 ^b	0.049	0.72 ^b	0.045
Adhesiveness (Ns)	Stage 5	4.29 ^a	0.14	4.19 ^a	0.07	4.02 ^a	0.09
	Stage 6	5.53 ^b	0.35	5.36 ^b	0.44	5.22 ^b	0.45
	Stage 7	6.63 ^c	0.22	6.50 ^c	0.13	6.39 ^c	0.11
Chewiness (N)	Stage 5	2.25 ^c	0.05	2.19 ^b	0.05	2.14 ^a	0.04
	Stage 6	2.03 ^c	0.16	1.96 ^b	0.22	1.90 ^a	0.23
	Stage 7	1.18 ^c	0.11	1.12 ^b	0.11	1.05 ^a	0.12
Stringiness (mm)	Stage 5	19.07 ^b	0.42	18.95 ^b	0.34	18.72 ^b	0.33
	Stage 6	18.40 ^a	0.62	17.97 ^a	0.88	17.89 ^a	0.84
	Stage 7	17.92 ^a	0.92	17.75 ^a	0.91	17.65 ^a	0.93
Fracturability (N)	Stage 5	11.71 ^c	0.53	11.58 ^c	0.62	11.45 ^c	0.65
	Stage 6	9.93 ^b	0.82	9.58 ^b	0.80	9.17 ^b	0.72
	Stage 7	5.22 ^a	0.95	5.04 ^a	0.89	4.96 ^a	0.88
Gumminess (N)	Stage 5	2.59 ^c	0.12	2.51 ^c	0.06	2.38 ^c	0.07
	Stage 6	2.35 ^b	0.34	2.26 ^b	0.28	2.19 ^b	0.31
	Stage 7	1.45 ^a	0.23	1.38 ^a	0.23	1.33 ^a	0.26

SD = standard deviation; Rows with the same common letter superscript are not significantly different at ($p \leq 0.05$), according to Duncan Multiple Range Test.

Figure 3. Changes in firmness of plantain finger during maturity. The columns with the same letter are not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) according to Duncan's multiple ranges test.

Figure 4. Changes in springiness of plantain finger during maturity. The columns with the same letter are not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) according to Duncan's multiple ranges test.

Figure 5. Changes in adhesiveness of plantain finger during maturity. The columns with the same letter are not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) according to Duncan's multiple ranges test.

Figure 6. Changes in gumminess of plantain finger during maturity. The columns with the same letter are not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) according to Duncan's multiple ranges test.

Figure 7. Changes in stringiness of plantain finger during maturity. The columns with the same letter are not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) according to Duncan's multiple ranges test.

Figure 8. Changes in fracturability of plantain finger during maturity. The columns with the same letter are not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) according to Duncan's multiple ranges test.

Figure 9. Changes in chewiness of plantain finger during maturity. The columns with the same letter are not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) according to Duncan's multiple ranges test.

breakdown of pectin substances and the movement of water from the rind of the banana to pulp during ripening and this could be the major cause for decreasing the various mechanical properties of banana during ripening.

Conclusion

The study was focused on the textural changes in plantain fingers particularly at the advanced maturity stages of 5, 6 and 7. From the results obtained, maturity stage had significant effect on the textural qualities of the plantain fingers, but no significant effect was observed among the three finger regions. Apart from the adhesiveness, the remaining six TPA parameters investigated decreased significantly from stage 5 to stage 7 of ripening. As shown in the results, the average fracturability of the fingers declined from 11.70 N to 5.22 N, while the firmness declined by 53.3% during ripening from stage 5 to stage 7. Furthermore, the fingers springiness decreased by 10.9%, while their average chewiness decreased significantly from 2.19 N at 5th stage to 1.12 N at 7th stage of ripening. These results obtained from this research would assist in effective planning of harvesting, transportation, processing operations of plantain bunches.

Authors' declaration

We declared that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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